

Report on End-to-End Dependable Communication over Multiple Network Domains

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Contributor(s):	Frank Dürr (USTUTT) Simon Egger (USTUTT) Lucas Haug (USTUTT) János Farkas (ETH) Balázs Varga (ETH)
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Reviewers:	Jose Costa Requena (CMC)
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Gourav Prateek Sharma (KTH)

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Disclaimer

This work has been performed in the framework of the Horizon Europe project DETERMINISTIC6G co-funded by the EU. This information reflects the consortium's view, but the consortium is not liable for any use that may be made of any of the information contained therein. This deliverable has been submitted to the EU commission, but it has not been reviewed and it has not been accepted by the EU commission yet.

Executive summary

In this report, we broaden the scope of our research on dependable end-to-end communication from a single network domain to **multiple network domains** (including domains with wireless 5G/6G logical bridges).

This report makes several key contributions to enable dependable end-to-end communication across multiple network domains:

- **System architecture for multi-domain systems:** This system architecture is specifically tailored to TSN networks, in particular TSN networks including logical 5G/6G TSN bridges. It builds on TSN concepts such as the fully centralized management of TSN domains, extended to multiple domains with a hierarchy of CNCs. Although the architecture is described with a focus on TSN, we also integrate DetNet concepts.
- **Aggregation concept for inter-domain streams:** To this end, we introduce so-called frame batches, aggregating frames from different intra-domain streams into a batch and handling them as a batch.
- **Inter-domain notification mechanism:** Notifications enable the coordination between neighboring domains, e.g., to allocate resources needed to forward streams that traverse multiple domains. This notification mechanism can operate on the network data plane, enabling the optimization of the domain entry/exit events and support minimizing the waste of resources especially for non-periodic streams/flows, like alarm signals, safety applications, etc.
- **Service protection mechanisms for multi-domain systems:** We describe basic principles of service protection like using multiple, redundant paths, and discuss how to apply such mechanisms to multi-domain systems and also within the 5G/6G system.
- **Inter-domain scheduling protocol and algorithms for calculating inter-domain (end-to-end) schedules:** Scheduling streams across domains brings up new questions, which are addressed in this report, such as, how to split the end-to-end latency budget between domains, or scheduling on aggregated streams.

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1 Introduction

Real-time communication with predictable bounds on end-to-end network delay and delay variation is an essential requirement for many cyber-physical systems. In particular, we are interested in cyber-physical systems including mobile devices as motivated by several use cases described in Deliverable D1.1 [DET23-D11] and D1.3 [DET25-D13], e.g., workers in a factory wearing exo-skeletons or eXtended Reality (XR) headsets, automated guided vehicles moving on a shop floor, or drones and vehicles in a smart farming use-case.

Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) and Deterministic Networking (DetNet) are standard technologies for real-time communication in such systems. With concepts like the logical 5G TSN bridge and wireless-friendly end-to-end scheduling mechanisms as described in Deliverable D3.1 [DET23-D31] and D3.4 [DET23-D34], dependable end-to-end real-time communication including wireless and wireline network elements is enabled. Although these proposed concepts support communication paths including both, wireless and wireline network elements, so far, we restricted our systems to a single network configuration domain. In this report, we widen the scope by considering multiple domains, where each domain is governed by its own centralized network controller (CNC), and focus on the overall question on how to support dependable end-to-end communication across multiple domains.

There are several reasons for multi-domain systems:

- *Autonomous administration and management:* each network domain can be administered and managed autonomously. For instance, a vendor of a larger machine (e.g. a paper printing machine or a harvester in a smart farming use case) might provide this machine with an integrated local network. To guarantee the correct operation of the machine, the vendor might be interested in keeping control over its local network and defines the local area network as a separate network domain, with well-defined interface (border bridge/router) to other networks.
- *Technological domains:* Also separating a system into domains along technological borders might be reasonable. For instance, a single 5G logical bridge including radio access network and core network can have a great geographical reach and specific internal operation and management procedures. Therefore, defining a dedicated (wireless) domain for the 5G system (logical TSN bridge) and connecting it to other (wired) domains at the core network can be beneficial from an administrative and management view.
- *Scalability:* Some control and management plane mechanisms might not scale to a large number of network elements, streams, etc. A prime example, which is also in the focus of this report, are the algorithms to calculate schedules for scheduled traffic according to IEEE 802.1Qbv in TSN (gate control lists for egress queues of TSN bridges). Calculating such schedules is an NP-hard problem with no efficient (polynomial) exact solution, i.e., exponential runtime in general. Besides the algorithmic complexity, these algorithms operate on a global view onto the network (network graph of stations, bridges, links) and traffic (streams) according to the fully-centralized model, which obviously induces overhead to collect global information from distributed elements depending on the size of network. Splitting the network into multiple domains allows for a "divide and conquer" approach, e.g., through a hierarchy of Centralized Network Controllers, where each controller controls and manages its individual domain. This reduces the size of individual domains, and consequently

mitigates the complexity and overhead of controlling and managing a smaller individual domain. Moreover, information to be exchanged between domains or with higher-level controllers (e.g., managing streams passing through several domains) can be aggregated to reduce its traffic volume and the required state each domain has to maintain.

- *Fault tolerance and service protection*: Factoring out parts of a network into individual domains can isolate the failures within one domain and prevent propagation of failures into other domains. For instance, each domain can have its own CNC. Moreover, it can be controlled, which traffic is leaving or entering a domain at its border. Similar to the idea of Frame Replication and Elimination (FRER) [IEEE17-8021CB] providing spatial redundancy and isolation (different paths) within a single domain, similar service protection mechanisms can be implemented across multiple domains. If redundant end-to-end paths via different disjunct domains can be found from source to destination in the inter-domain topology, end-to-end reliability can be increased by routing messages redundantly via different domains.

The goal of this report is to investigate different aspects of multi-domain systems. In detail, we present the following:

- A **system architecture for multi-domain systems**, building on and compatible with TSN technology, including also logical 5G/6G bridges.
- An **aggregation concept for inter-domain streams**.
- An **inter-domain notification mechanism**.
- **Service protection mechanisms for multi-domain systems**.
- An **inter-domain scheduling protocol and algorithms for calculating inter-domain (end-to-end) schedules**.

In the remainder of this section, we present an overview of the overall DETERMINISTIC6G approach in which the multi-domain research of this report is embedded, the objectives of this report, its relation to other work packages, and an outline of the rest of this report.

1.1 DETERMINISTIC6G Approach

Digital transformation of industries and society is resulting in the emergence of a larger family of time-critical services with needs for high availability and which present unique requirements distinct from traditional Internet applications like video streaming or web browsing. Time-critical services are already known in industrial automation; for example, an industrial control application that might require an end-to-end “over the loop” (i.e., from the sensor to the controller back to the actuator) latency of 2 ms and with a communication service requirement of 99.9999 % [3GPP23-22261]. With the increasing digitalization, similar requirements are appearing in a growing number of new application domains, such as extended reality, autonomous vehicles, and adaptive manufacturing. The general long-term trend of digitalization leads towards a Cyber-Physical Continuum where the monitoring, control and maintenance functionality is moved from physical objects (like a robot, a machine, or a tablet device) to a compute platform at some other location, where a digital representation – or digital twin – of the object is operated. Such Cyber Physical System (CPS) applications need a frequent and consistent information exchange between the digital and physical twins. Several technology developments in the ICT-sector drive this transition. The proliferation of the (edge-)cloud compute paradigm provides new cost-efficient and scalable computing capabilities, which are often more efficient to maintain and evolve compared to embedded compute solutions

integrated into the physical objects. It also enables the creation of digital twins as a tool for advanced monitoring, prediction, and automation of system components and improved coordination of systems of systems. New techniques based on Machine Learning can be applied in application design, which can operate over large data sets and profit from scalable compute infrastructure. Offloading compute functionality can also reduce spatial footprint, weight, cost, and energy consumption of physical objects, which is in particular important for mobile components, like vehicles, mobile robots, or wearable devices. This approach leads to an increasing need for communication between physical and digital objects, and this communication can span over multiple communication and computational domains. Communication in this cyber-physical world often includes closed-loop control interactions that can have stringent end-to-end KPIs (e.g., minimum, and maximum packet delay) requirements over the entire loop. In addition, many operations may have high criticality, such as business-critical tasks or even safety relevant operations. Therefore, it is required to provide dependable time-critical communication that provides communication service-assurance to achieve the agreed service requirements.

Time-critical communication has in the past been mainly prevalent in industrial automation scenarios with special compute hardware like Programmable Logic Controllers (PLC), and based on proprietary, mutually incompatible wired communication technologies, such as Powerlink and EtherCat, which are limited to local and isolated network domains and which are configured to the specific purpose of the local applications. With the standardization of TSN and Deterministic Networking (DetNet), similar capabilities are being introduced into Ethernet and IP networking technologies, which thereby provide a converged multi-service network enabling time critical applications in a managed network infrastructure allowing for consistent performance with zero packet loss and guaranteed low and bounded latency. The underlying principles are that the network elements (i.e. bridges or routers) and the PLCs can provide a consistent and known performance with negligible stochastic variation, which allows to manage the network configuration to the needs of time-critical applications with known traffic characteristics and requirements. Furthermore, using interchangeable TSN hardware components has economic benefits, avoids vendor lock-in, and enables third-party support for configuration and troubleshooting.

It turns out that several elements in the digitalization journey introduce characteristics that deviate from the assumptions that are considered as baseline in the planning of deterministic networks. There is often an assumption that for compute and communication elements and also applications any stochastic behavior can be minimized such that the time characteristics of the element can be clearly associated with tight minimum/maximum bounds. Cloud computing provides efficient scalable computing, but introduces uncertainty in execution times; wireless communications provides flexibility and simplicity, but with inherently stochastic components that lead to packet delay variations exceeding significantly those found in wired counterparts; and applications embrace novel technologies (e.g. ML-based or machine-vision-based control) where the traffic characteristics deviate from the strictly deterministic behavior of old-school control. In addition, there will be an increase in dynamic behavior where characteristics of applications and network or compute elements may change over time in contrast to a static behavior that does not change during runtime. It turns out that these deviations of stochastic characteristics make traditional approaches to planning and configuration of end-to-end time-critical communication networks such as TSN or DetNet fall short in their performance regarding service performance, scalability, and efficiency. Instead, a revolutionary approach to the design, planning, and operation of time-critical networks is needed that fully

embraces the variability but also dynamic changes that come at the side of introducing wireless connectivity, cloud computing, and application innovation. DETERMINISTIC6G has as objective to address these challenges, including the planning of resource allocation for diverse time-critical services end-to-end, over multiple domains, providing efficient resource usage and a scalable solution [SPS+23].

DETERMINISTIC6G takes a novel approach towards converged future infrastructures for scalable cyber-physical systems deployment. With respect to networked infrastructures, DETERMINISTIC6G advocates: (I) the acceptance and integration of stochastic elements (like wireless links and computational elements) with respect to their stochastic behavior captured through either short-term or longer-term envelopes. Monitoring and prediction of KPIs, for instance latency or reliability, can be leveraged to make individual elements plannable despite a remaining stochastic variance. Nevertheless, system enhancements to mitigate stochastic variances in communication and compute elements are also developed. (II) Next, DETERMINISTIC6G attempts the management of the entire end-to-end interaction loop (e.g. the control loop) with the underlying stochastic characteristics, especially embracing the integration of compute elements. (III) Finally, due to unavoidable stochastic degradations of individual elements, DETERMINISTIC6G advocates for allowing adaptation between applications running over such converged and managed network infrastructures. The idea is to introduce flexibility in the application operation such that its requirements can be adjusted at runtime based on prevailing system conditions. This encompasses a larger set of application requirements that (a) can also accept stochastic end-to-end KPIs, and (b) possibly can adapt end-to-end KPI requirements at run-time in harmonization with the networked infrastructure. DETERMINISTIC6G builds on a notion of time-awareness, by ensuring accurate and reliable time synchronicity while also ensuring security-by-design for such dependable time-critical communications. Generally, a notion of deterministic communication (where all behavior of network and compute nodes and applications is pre-determined) is extended towards dependable time-critical communication, where the focus is on ensuring that the communication (and compute) characteristics are managed in order to provide the KPIs and reliability levels that are required by the application. DETERMINISTIC6G facilitates architectures and algorithms for scalable and converged future network infrastructures that enable dependable time-critical communication end-to-end, across domains and including 6G.

This report is specifically focused on the *multi-domain* aspects of dependable end-to-end communication. In the next sub-section, we provide an overview of the contributions to enable such dependable end-to-end communication across domains.

1.2 Contributions of the Report

This report makes several key contributions to enable dependable end-to-end communication across multiple network domains:

- **System architecture for multi-domain systems:** This system architecture is specifically tailored to TSN networks, in particular TSN networks including logical 5G/6G TSN bridges. It builds on TSN concepts such as the fully centralized management of TSN domains, which are extended to multiple domains with a hierarchy of CNCs. Although the architecture is described with a focus on TSN, we also integrate DetNet concepts.

- **Aggregation concept for inter-domain streams:** We introduce so-called frame batches, aggregating frames from different intra-domain streams into batches and handling them together as batches, in particular for inter-domain scheduling.
- **Inter-domain notification mechanism:** This notification mechanism operates on the network data plane, enabling the optimization of the domain entry/exit events and supports minimizing the waste of resources, especially for non-periodic streams/flows, like alarm signals, safety applications, etc.
- **Service protection mechanisms for multi-domain systems:** We describe basic principles of service protection like using multiple redundant paths, and discuss how to apply such mechanisms to multi-domain systems and also within the 5G/6G system.
- **Inter-domain scheduling protocol and algorithms for calculating inter-domain (end-to-end) schedules:** Scheduling streams across domains brings up new questions, which are addressed in this report, such as, how to split the end-to-end latency budget between domains, or scheduling on aggregated streams.

1.3 Relation to Other Work Packages

The approaches presented in this report have been designed in **WP3**. Previously, we have already addressed dependable end-to-end scheduling in single domains in WP3 in D3.1 [DET23-D31] and the adaptation of end-to-end schedules in D3.4 [DET23-D34]. Besides these work-package-internal relations within WP3, this report has several relations to other work packages and deliverables (see Figure 1):

- **WP1:** The multi-domain concepts discussed in this report are motivated by the use-cases from WP1, which have been described in D1.1 [DET23-D11] and D1.3 [DET25-D13]. Moreover, the presented multi-domain concepts are embedded into the DETERMINISTIC6G architecture designed in WP1. A first version of the architecture has been described in D1.2 [DET24-D12]. The integration of multiple domains is subject to the future deliverable D1.4, which will describe the final architecture.
- **WP2:** WP2 develops 6G-centric enablers for dependable communication. These concepts include time-synchronization (D2.2 [DET23-D22]), the mitigation of packet delay variation through packet delay correction (D2.1 [DET23-D21] and D2.3 [DET25-D23]), or packet delay prediction. All these concepts are the foundation of dependable end-to-end communication, both for intra-domain end-to-end scheduling and also for inter-domain scheduling.
- **WP4:** WP4 develops the validation framework based on experiments and network simulation. In particular, end-to-end scheduling mechanisms are subject to validation through end-to-end simulations (D4.1 [DET23-D41]), also based on latency measurements from D4.2 [DET24-D42] and D4.3 [DET25-D43].

Figure 1: Relation to other work packages

1.4 Structure and Scope of the Document

The rest of this report is structured as follows: Section 2 is focused on the system architecture and system concepts of multi-domain systems including a concept for stream aggregation, an inter-domain scheduling protocol, and an inter-domain notification mechanism. Section 3 presents service-protection mechanisms for multi-domain systems. Section 4 presents algorithms for inter-domain end-to-end scheduling, before we conclude the report in Section 5.

2 System Architecture and Concepts for Multi-Domain Systems

In this section, we first present a system architecture of a multi-domain system, which also serves as a system model to define our assumptions for the concepts presented in the following, namely, an aggregation concept for inter-domain streams, an inter-domain scheduling protocol, and an inter-domain notification mechanism.

2.1 Multi-Domain System Model

We consider Time-Sensitive Networks with multiple administration/*configuration domains* (henceforth simply referred to as domain), where each domain is managed and configured by its own centralized network/user controller (CNC/CUC). Similarly, each domain can provide additional management-related services like troubleshooting, maintenance, or monitoring that can be coordinated by the domain's CNC. An overview of this architecture is shown in Figure 2. In general, the configuration domains may or may not be equal to the time synchronization domains. For the scope of this document, however, we assume that devices within a configuration domain are

synchronized. A time synchronization domain can therefore span over one or multiple configuration domains. Further time synchronization requirements are discussed explicitly in Section 2.2.

Figure 2: System architecture of Time-Sensitive Networks with multiple configuration domains

We differentiate between *intra-domain* and *inter-domain* TSN streams: For intra-domain streams, the talker and all listeners are located within the same domain. This allows the domain’s CNC to have full control over the employed routing (path reservation), replication, and traffic shaping mechanisms for intra-domain streams. In contrast, inter-domain streams have at least one listener that resides in a different domain than the talker. Consequently, inter-domain streams require a higher-level entity that coordinates the resource allocation for each domain. To this end, we consider a dedicated *inter-domain controller* with an aggregated global view onto the network for this task. To improve scalability, we do not require the inter-domain controller to have a fine-grained view of each network device and each intra-/inter-domain stream; instead, we discuss suitable aggregation concepts from a system architecture perspective in Section 2.3.

For the scope of this document, we exclusively consider time-triggered streams that are characterized by a fixed transmission period, a minimum/maximum frame size, and an end-to-end Quality of Service (QoS) requirement in the form of latency, reliability, and jitter. We denote time-triggered streams by F_1, F_2, \dots and corresponding frames of a stream F by $f_1, f_2, \dots \in F$. A time-triggered schedule then provides a fixed receival interval $[rx_1(f_i), rx_2(f_i)]$ for each frame $f_i \in F$. We say that the schedule is feasible if it satisfies the QoS requirements of all streams:

- For each stream F and each frame $f_i \in F$, the probability of f_i arriving in the intended arrival interval $[rx_1(f_i), rx_2(f_i)]$ exceeds the required reliability requirement of F . Moreover, the latency requirement of F yields an upper-bound for $rx_2(f_i)$ whereas the jitter requirement of F is an upper-bound for $rx_2(f_i) - rx_1(f_i)$.

2.2 Relaxation of Time Synchronization Requirements

Devices within each configuration domain are assumed to be synchronized with IEEE 802.1AS to provide a bounded clock skew of 1us for any two devices within *100 wireline hops* of each other [IEC/IEEE24-60802]. However, for inter-domain streams that traverse multiple domains, potentially with both wired and wireless network elements, it may not be feasible to satisfy these stringent time

synchronization requirements. We therefore distinguish between TSN domains that are strongly synchronized, loosely synchronized, or unsynchronized w.r.t. to their neighboring domains.

- A TSN domain D is *strongly synchronized* to all other domains N_1, N_2, \dots, N_k if the clock skew of any two devices $v_1 \in D, v_2 \in N_i$ (for some $1 \leq i \leq k$) is bounded by $1\mu s$.
- A TSN domain D is *loosely synchronized* to its neighboring domains N_1, N_2, \dots, N_k , if the clock skew of any two border TSN bridges $v_1 \in \text{border_bridges}(D), v_2 \in \text{border_bridges}(N_i)$ (for some $1 \leq i \leq k$) is bounded by some fixed Δ , which is potentially greater than $1\mu s$.
- Otherwise, the TSN domain D is unsynchronized to its neighboring domains.

The difference between strongly synchronized and loosely synchronized is best seen when considering the end-to-end synchronization of talkers and listeners: Consider an inter-domain stream that traverses N domains. If all of these domains are strongly synchronized with each other, then the clock skew of the talker and listener is bounded by $1\mu s$ as well. If the domains are loosely synchronized, however, this bound increases to

$$N \times 1\mu s + (N - 1) \times \Delta.$$

In the first domain, the clock skew between talker and the border TSN bridge is bounded by $1\mu s$. The same holds for every intermediate domain (from ingress to egress border TSN bridge) and for the last domain (from ingress border TSN bridge to the listener). In contrast, every domain transition (out of the $N - 1$ transitions) may introduce an additional clock skew of Δ .

In this work, we provide different scheduling solutions based on the underlying domain capabilities. While it is apparent that not every scheduling approach is applicable for unsynchronized domains (e.g., most IEEE 802.1Qbv schedulers assume synchronized devices), we argue that most of the presented techniques are applicable to networks with loosely synchronized TSN domains. We stress, however, that the application's performance may still suffer from large bounds Δ (e.g., for coordination tasks that require synchronous motion control for all actuators). Consequently, we leave the exact specification of the time synchronization requirements to depend on the needs of the applications, whereas our scheduling approaches are generally designed to work with arbitrary bounds for loose synchronization. For the remainder of this work, we assume at least loosely synchronized domains if not stated otherwise.

2.3 Aggregation of Inter-Domain Streams

If streams traverse several domains, it is beneficial to aggregate stream information (e.g., the streams' specifications in form of periodicity, latency, and reliability requirements) to increase scalability and to reduce scheduling complexity. We say that two frames f_1 and f_2 are aggregated into a frame batch $B = \{f_1, f_2\}$ if an intermediate TSN domain does not need to differentiate between the two respective streams F_1 and F_2 but treats the frames as if they were from the same (aggregate) stream. Moreover, the intermediate TSN domains do not need to enforce a specific frame ordering between streams F_1 and F_2 within a batch (e.g., at an elimination point of FRER), but may simply forward them on a first in, first out (FIFO) basis.¹

¹ For simplicity, we therefore assume that there is at most one frame per stream within each batch.

In this sub-section, we first discuss the benefits of stream aggregation and afterwards show different options of stream aggregation and how to implement them in TSN and DetNet.

2.3.1 Benefits of Stream Aggregation

Two main reasons for stream aggregation are to increase scalability and to reduce complexity. From an algorithmic perspective, IEEE 802.1Qbv scheduling is a complex problem closely related to the job-shop scheduling problem, which is an NP-hard constrained optimization problem. In particular, the difficulty of the scheduling instance is related to the number of contesting frame transmissions per egress port, i.e., the schedule has to decide the transmission ordering of frames over each egress port. By aggregating multiple streams into a stream batch, this scheduling decision is bypassed by explicitly allowing frame reordering within a batch, reducing scheduling complexity as a result. Similarly, scalability is also increased by storing less state information (e.g., needed by fault tolerance mechanisms like PSFP and FRER) in nodes since aggregation typically reduces the granularity of information and hides detailed stream information from other domains.

To reduce complexity, aggregation also simplifies the addition and removal of streams, as not every domain requires global knowledge of all streams, and adding or removing individual streams does not necessarily imply rescheduling for the entire network. In particular, with a fixed resource allocation per domain for certain traffic classes (see Section 2.4.4), adding streams becomes a packing problem. Finally, aggregation also allows for the separation of responsibilities of operators. For instance, the local CNC of a domain can exclusively plan traffic shaping for its own domain.

2.3.2 Aggregation Options in the TSN/DetNet Data Plane

After having motivated the benefits of stream aggregation in the previous sub-section, we present and discuss different general options of aggregation and how to implement aggregation in TSN and DetNet next. Aggregation can take place within a network node, when that node maintains state about both, the aggregated and individual flows. It can also take place between nodes, when one node maintains state about only flow aggregates while the other node maintains state on all or a portion of the individual flows. During aggregation, it must be ensured that aggregated flows have compatible (e.g., the same or very similar) QoS and/or Class of Service (CoS) characteristics; otherwise, the per-flow service requirements cannot be satisfied by the aggregate.

Two flavors of aggregation can be distinguished:

1. Option-1: Forwarding-bundle of streams/flows. A bundle is a simplified form of aggregation, where the aggregate is used to simplify the reservation/usage of network forwarding resources (e.g., identification, bandwidth, queuing, congestion control). This simplified aggregate lacks the metadata needed for more complex dependability service entities, like service protection via replication & elimination. From data plane encapsulation perspective the forwarding-bundle is created via a simple “tunneling” technique — e.g., in TSN using Provider Bridging (adding an S-Tag with additional VLAN control information); in DetNet (MPLS) for aggregation via Label-Switched Path (LSP) Hierarchy.
2. Option-2: Aggregate as a new stream/flow. This form of aggregation adds metadata as well to the aggregate, which allows the configuration/usage of the same toolset for the aggregate, which can be used by the individual streams/flows. From data plane encapsulation perspective, the aggregate is created via an “intelligent-tunneling” technique, where metadata is also added during the tunneling — e.g., in TSN using Provider Bridging (S-Tag)

plus a new replication tag (R-Tag) with a sequence number field; in DetNet (MPLS) the same principle applies for aggregating DetNet Flows as a New DetNet Flow with a so-called “A-Label + d-CW”.

The basic data plane options for TSN/DetNet aggregation flavors use the following technologies:

1. TSN: Provider Bridging (PB)
2. DetNet: MPLS, IP.

FRER in Customer Network (no FRER in PB)

- FRER in Customer Network operates in on Customer’s R-tag (Customer’s FRER domain)

- FRER operates as usual on C-VLAN space

FRER in Provider Network (separated from Customer)

- FRER in Provider Network operates in on Provider’s R-tag (Provider’s FRER domain)

- FRER operates just like before, but on S-VLAN space (only on S-VLAN space) as all after S-VID is practically payload

Figure 3: Location of the R-Tag in customer and provider networks.

In the TSN standards there are no explicit aggregation specific sections. TSN functions are defined as an add-on to Ethernet networks, so aggregation can be achieved using existing IEEE functionalities. Aggregation in TSN networks has the following characteristics:

- Encapsulation format for aggregates:
 - It is based on header manipulation (VID: VLAN-ID) using Provider Bridging. Aggregation / de-aggregation is achieved by adding/removing an S-Tag (and an R-Tag if needed) to the existing Ethernet header of the frame.
- Service protection for the new aggregate Stream:
 - Service Protection requires the usage of a new replication/elimination (R/E) level, i.e., adding a new aggregate specific R-Tag to the Ethernet header.
- Encoding Stream specific information:
 - Stream identification for aggregate is based on the pushed S-VID.
 - Sequence Number is added by a new R-Tag, which is placed behind the S-VID if FRER is configured on the aggregate stream.
 - Original stream(s) can be identified during de-aggregation, based on the original header, src-MAC, dst-MAC, C-VID, etc.
- Design prerequisites / limitations:
 - Both aggregation options can be achieved; it is a matter of adding or leaving out the aggregate specific R-Tag.
 - Provider Bridging (PB) design impacts essentially the aggregation possibilities. PB was defined to allow for a hierarchical L2 network design by creating a “backbone” domain in the Ethernet infrastructure.
 - Aggregation-related intentions have to be considered during the PB network design, i.e., S-VID topology have to match the planned aggregation/de-aggregation points for the TSN streams.
 - Serving a mixture of aggregated and non-aggregated TSN streams in Ethernet networks is not trivial.

Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the usage of PB encapsulation for aggregation and the location of the R-Tag in the various encapsulations.

Using FRER in Both Networks

Figure 4: PB encapsulation used for aggregation and the location of the R-Tag

The standardization of DetNet targeted aggregation explicitly from its beginning (see e.g., RFC 8655, Section 4.9 “Scaling to Larger Networks”), therefore aggregation is defined in detail in all the related data plane RFCs/drafts. (Note that not all data plane possibilities are covered, like various formats of tunneling (e.g., GRE, IPinIP) are not precluded, but not discussed in the IETF DetNet WG.)

Aggregation in DetNet networks has the following characteristics:

- Encapsulation format for aggregates:
 - In case of an MPLS data plane a specific DetNet-PW encapsulation is used.
 - In case of IP data plane there are multiple options: native IP, DetNet-PW over UDP, and various tunneling options.
- Service protection for the new aggregate flow:
 - Service protection requires the usage of a new R/E level (e.g., implemented via a new additional aggregate specific d-CW).
- Encoding of the stream-specific information is defined in:
 - RFC8655: DetNet Architecture
 - RFC8964: DetNet Data Plane: MPLS
 - RFC8939: DetNet Data Plane: IP
 - RFC9566: DetNet PREOF via MPLS over UDP/IP
 - draft-varga-detnet-srv6-data-plane (for SRv6 encapsulation)
- Design prerequisites / limitations:
 - In scenarios using the DetNet-PW (MPLS) encapsulation:
 - Any DetNet node can aggregate/de-aggregate DetNet flows if it implements the standard aggregation function.
 - Both aggregation option can be achieved:
 - Option-1: aggregation via LSP Hierarchy (no aggregate specific d-CW)
 - Option-2: aggregating with an A-Label + aggregate specific d-CW

- In scenarios using the DetNet (IP) encapsulation:
 - Any DetNet node can aggregate/de-aggregate DetNet flows if it implements the standard aggregation function.
 - Aggregation options can be achieved as follows:
 - Option-1: this option is supported using the native IP encapsulation. Identification is based on 6-tuples (wildcards, masks, lists, prefixes, and ranges are allowed), or using additional tunneling (e.g., UDP/IP tunnel).
 - Option-2: this option requires specific encapsulation formats in order to add the aggregate specific sequence number to the DetNet packet. One alternative is the usage of a DetNet-PW over UDP, which practically means the combination of MPLS and IP technologies. Another alternative is the usage of SRv6, but it is still work in progress and can be used only in IPv6 networks.
- Aggregation can be easily added to an existing network design by the selective upgrade of nodes with aggregation/de-aggregation capabilities. There are no restrictions like in TSN with the PB technology.
- Serving a mixture of aggregated and non-aggregated DetNet flows is simple.

Figure 5 shows two Option-2 flavor aggregation examples for the two DetNet data planes.

Figure 5: Option-2 aggregation examples for the DetNet (MPLS, IP) data planes [RFC8964, RFC9566].

2.4 Inter-Domain Scheduling Protocol

Next, we propose an inter-domain scheduling protocol to schedule streams end-to-end across domains.

To this end, we split the multi-domain scheduling procedure into multiple steps:

1. *Stream Advertisement*: Each data source (resp. sink) advertises its stream characteristics (resp. requirements) at the domain's CUC. If eligible, the advertisement is forwarded to the inter-domain controller.

2. *Multipoint Stream Aggregation*: Data sources and sinks are grouped into a multipoint tree according to their stream characteristics and requirements.
3. *Latency Budget Splitting*: The inter-domain controller splits the end-to-end latency budget along the forwarding path to provide each domain with a release time and a deadline.
4. *Per-Domain Stream Aggregation and Scheduling*: Instead of providing each TSN domain with every stream specification, the inter-domain controller can batch multiple streams if their per-domain release time and deadline are not conflicting. Each domain then tries to incorporate the inter-domain stream batches into its TSN configuration.
5. *Inter-Domain Scheduling Decision*: The inter-domain controller notifies the CUC responsible for the data source and data sinks with the scheduling decision. A source-sink pair is accepted if and only if all domains along the multipoint path accepted the stream.

In the following, we provide further details on the individual steps.

2.4.1 Stream Advertisements and Subscriptions

Each data source (talker) of a TSN stream advertises its stream specification at the domain’s CUC. For instance, with the stream specifications of [Table 46-8, IEEE22-8021Q], the stream’s specification may consist of a maximum sampling frequency (i.e., a lower-bound on the periodicity), along with a lower- and upper-bound for the frame sizes. Moreover, the talker provides a type identifier to specify which kind of data (e.g., control messages, sensor streams, closed-loop data streams, or diagnostics) is produced. The CUC then forwards the inter-domain stream advertisement to the inter-domain controller, where it is stored in a global stream registry. For example, an end-station in Figure 6 may advertise two streams (id = 1, period = 10ms, size = 100B) and (id = 5, period = 5ms, size = 200B) to the domain’s CUC. While stream 1 is eligible as an inter-domain stream, stream 5 may reference some internal control stream that should not be exposed outside its domain; consequently, the domain’s CUC solely forwards the advertisement of stream 1 to the inter-domain controller.

Figure 6 Intra-/Inter-domain stream registry

Similarly, each listener (data sink) sends a subscription (consumption request) with a type identifier to the domain’s CNC. Consumption requests also specify the required quality of service (QoS), e.g., minimum sampling frequency, minimum reliability, maximum latency, and maximum jitter, that is

expected by the data sink. We consider a simple approach that uses predefined QoS classes that cover a suitable range of sampling frequencies and reliability/latency requirements. For instance, a consumption request ($id = 2, QoS = Class B$) can match the type identifier of either an intra-domain or inter-domain stream, as long as the QoS requirements of *Class B* are satisfied. In the next step, this information is used to find suitable matches between stream advertisements and consumption requests.

2.4.2 Multipoint Tree Aggregation

With considerable scheduling and reconfiguration overhead, it is impractical to change the network configuration for each individual stream advertisement and consumption request. Instead, we consider epoch-based updates that allow the domains' CNCs/CUCs and the inter-domain controller to aggregate multiple advertisements and requests. After an epoch, both the previous and new entries in the intra-/inter-domain stream registries are considered to match data sources, and data sinks are matched based on their type identifiers and their QoS class.

Figure 7: Multipoint aggregation for a stream F with listeners in two domains $D_{L_1}(F)$ and $D_{L_2}(F)$.

Instead of handling each source-sink pair as a unicast stream, multiple consumption requests can be combined based on the QoS requirements of the data sinks. For each inter-domain stream F , this provides the inter-domain controller with the domain of the talker $D_T(F)$ and the domains of the listeners $D_L = \{D_{L_1}(F), D_{L_2}(F), \dots, D_{L_k}(F)\}$. With the global view of the network domains and border TSN bridges, the inter-domain controller can then compute one or multiple multipoint forwarding trees with $D_T(F)$ as the root and D_L as the leaf nodes. For each domain transition, the forwarding tree must also specify which border TSN bridge to traverse. Further details on how suitable multipoint trees can be computed (including inter-domain replication) are provided in Section 3.

Figure 7 illustrates this procedure for a stream advertisement from domain $D_T(F)$. There are two consumption requests from listeners in the domains $D_{L_1}(F)$ and $D_{L_2}(F)$ that are deemed suitable to match with F . Importantly, the QoS class of the different listener domains may differ depending on the number of intermediate domains, e.g., the latency experienced by $D_{L_2}(F)$ can be considerably

larger than for $D_{L_1}(F)$. To increase the reliability that frames of F are delivered to $D_{L_2}(F)$ within the required latency bounds, the inter-domain controller allocates two paths via different transit domains.

2.4.3 Latency Budget Splitting

With the multipoint tree in place, the next step is to split the end-to-end latency into multiple budgets for each domain that is traversed. For instance, if QoS Class C from Figure 7 requires an end-to-end latency of $10ms$, a uniform budget splitting provides each domain with $2.5ms$. For the transit domain between (2a) and (3a), this provides an effective release time at $5ms$ and an effective deadline at $7.5ms$. More involved budget splitting techniques are later discussed in Section 4.

2.4.4 Per-Domain Stream Aggregation

Figure 8: Per-domain stream aggregation.

Based on the computed multipoint trees and the end-to-end latency splittings, the inter-domain controller can combine multiple streams into a stream aggregate, as shown in Figure 8. This refers to the option "Aggregate as a new Stream/Flow" described in Section 2.3, where the additional S-Tags and R-Tags are pushed at the ingress border bridges and popped at the egress border bridges. During transit within the domain, the S-Tag allows the TSN bridges to identify the stream aggregate, while the R-Tags can be used for intra-domain replication.

There is an apparent tradeoff between prioritizing the individual inter-domain stream QoS guarantees and prioritizing the level of aggregation to reduce the state information that is stored at each TSN bridge. To this end, we present two options, along with their advantages and disadvantages:

1. **Stream-based Aggregation:** Determine the end-to-end latency budget splitting for each inter-domain stream to compute the release times and deadlines for each intermediate TSN domain. Based on this information, iteratively try to merge multiple streams into a stream aggregate. Two streams F_1 and F_2 are compatible to be merged in domain D if
 - (i) $F_1.period$ and $F_2.period$ are harmonic, i.e., $F_1.period$ divides $F_2.period$ or the other way around, and
 - (ii) the release times and deadlines are not conflicting, i.e., neither $D(F_1).release > D(F_2).deadline$ nor $D(F_2).release > D(F_1).deadline$.

With this policy, stream aggregation is clearly a secondary goal as it is only done if it does not create release time or deadline conflicts. While, from a scheduling perspective, this increases the solution space to find an “optimal” schedule, it can also lead to a state explosion where each TSN bridge has to keep state information on most inter-domain streams.

2. **Class-based Aggregation:** As an alternative, it is also possible to introduce a small number of service classes (e.g., Gold, Silver, Bronze) that every inter-domain stream has to be assigned to. This creates an optimization problem that is closely related to bin-packing. Each service class is characterized (similar to time-triggered streams) by a period, phase, and latency that provides a QoS guarantee within the domain. The main advantage is that the required state information, to be stored in every TSN bridge to support inter-domain streams, is strictly limited to the number of provided service classes. However, this may lead to violated deadlines in the previously determined end-to-end latency budget splitting. This requires a budget rebalancing across multiple domains that needs to be supported by the budget splitting algorithm. We discuss possible approaches in Section 4.3.

2.4.5 Inter-Domain Scheduling Decision

Finally, the inter-domain controller forwards the stream aggregate specifications to each domain (in particular the CNC of each domain). Therefore, each CNC has now a set of time-triggered streams, stream aggregates, and/or service classes for which it tries to find a feasible schedule. We will discuss how the needed aggregation and replication concepts can be supported by the local scheduling algorithms in Section 4.4. If the local schedule cannot support all inter-domain streams, the local CNC prioritizes the intra-domain streams and higher-priority service classes, while rejecting lower-priority service classes or lower-priority inter-domain streams. Afterwards, the CNCs notify the inter-domain controller of the local scheduling decisions (i.e., which inter-domain streams are accepted, and which are rejected). Finally, the inter-domain controller accumulates all scheduling decisions and accepts an inter-domain stream if and only if all intermediate domains accepted its respective stream aggregate or service class. Similar to the two-phase commit, the inter-domain controller propagates this global decision to all domains before the per-domain schedules become operational.

2.5 Inter-Domain Notification Mechanism

Previous sections have described the control- and management-plane-related interactions between the domains and the controllers. They work on a stream/flow time scale and target the addition/modification/removal of streams/flows. There is a further mode of inter-domain notification possibilities, whose aim is to support the data plane forwarding. These notification solutions work at packet time scale, and they are related to the arrival/departure of events of packets at the domain borders. They can smoothen the forwarding’s differences between the various domain technologies and can provide a more wireless-friendly end-to-end design.

Inter-domain data plane notification mechanisms allow for simpler optimization of the domain entry/exit events and support minimizing the waste of resources especially for non-periodic streams/flows (e.g., like alarm signals for safety applications).

There are two possible inter-domain data plane notifications described here in more detail. Both notifications are exchanged between the border bridges of the connected domains, and they trigger the connected domain to start preparation for the transport of time critical traffic:

- “Packet Arrives Soon” notification

- “Ready for Packet Delivery” notification

Both types of notifications realize a one-way communication pattern that can be implemented in a stateless manner. In the following, we assume notifications are sent to a directly connected neighbor. While intermediate nodes are not prohibited between the communicating entities, included timing information will grow inaccurate over multiple hops with uncertain packet delays.

“Packet Arrives Soon” Notification

We start with three use cases, where “Packet Arrives Soon” notifications can be useful:

- Use-case 1: “Packet Arrives” signal for inter-domain synchronization (e.g., as later detailed in Section 4.3.2)
 - A host communication module informs the connected neighbor/domain.
 - Neighbor can prepare for forwarding (e.g., ask the 5G/6G scheduler for grants).
- Use-case 2: “IEEE 802.1Qbv state specific” notification
 - Inform the next-hop, that a queue open event will happen soon.
 - Neighbor can prepare for forwarding (note: can learn Qbv cycle pattern as well)
- Use-case 3: “Inter-domain” notification
 - Edge node informs connected domain, that packets will be sent soon.
 - Connected domain can start preparation for forwarding.

“Packet Arrives Soon” notifications have the same direction as the stream/flow they are related to, and they can contain the following information elements:

- Type: defines how to interpret the notification (e.g., “Aperiodic Stream” info, “Periodic Stream” info, “Qbv gate open event” info)
- Stream-ID/Flow-ID/TC-ID/Q-ID: the traffic/queue the notification relates to (note: flow can be an aggregate as well [TC: traffic class, Q: queue])
- Start of sending: when the signaled packets can be expected (note: this is more like an inter-packet gap, not a time-stamp, e.g., 0.5 ms after the arrival of the notification packet)
- Traffic volume (optional): how much traffic is expected (note: if this information is known, e.g., 5 packets, 2.500 bytes)

These parameters can be defined in type-length-value (TLV) format to allow flexibility. A notification packet may contain multiple notification types and TLVs.

Figure 9 shows the usage of the “Packet Arrives Soon” notification, where the connected domain is a 5G system. The trigger notification from the Actor allows the preparation for the forwarding over the radio link, immediately when the data packet arrives.

Figure 9: "Packet Arrives Soon" notification

"Ready for Packet Delivery" Notification

Next, we consider Ready for Packer Delivery notifications. As examples, three use cases are listed next, where "Ready for Packet Delivery" notification can be useful:

- Use-case 1: "Ready to receive packet" signal
 - Connected node/host is ready to receive packets (e.g., 5G/6G scheduler allocated grants or for the Release Guard Protocol in Section 4.3.2)
- Use-case 2: IEEE 802.1Qci state specific notification
 - Inform previous-hop, that a gate open event will happen soon
 - Neighbor can start forwarding (note: neighbor can learn Qci cycle pattern as well)
- Use-case 3: Inter-domain notification
 - Edge node informs connected domain, that packets can be sent

The "Ready for Packet Delivery" notification has the reverse direction as the stream/flow it is related to, and it can contain the following information elements:

- Type: defines how to interpret the notification (e.g., Deliver, EndHost, Qci gate info)
- Stream-ID/Flow-ID/TC-ID/Q-ID: the traffic/queue it relates to (note: flow can be an aggregate as well [TC: traffic class, Q: queue])
- Start of receiving (optional): when the data packets can be expected, if not specified "dt=0" can be used, i.e., immediate transmission. (Note: this is more like an inter-packet gap information, not a time-stamp, e.g., 0.5 ms after the arrival of the notification packet)
- Traffic volume (optional): how much traffic is expected to be received (e.g., 5 packets, 2.500 bytes)

These parameters can also be defined in TLV format to allow flexibility.

Figure 10 shows the usage of the “Ready for Packet Delivery” notification, where the connected domain is a 5G system. The trigger notification from the switch (SW) after the 5G system allows the 5G node (UPF) to send the packet according to the setup of the connected TSN domain.

Figure 10: “Ready for Packet Delivery” notification

3 Service Protection for Multi-Domains Systems

Service protection mechanisms are used to mitigate the impact of network events resulting in packet loss, e.g., (random) media errors or equipment failures. In the case of deterministic or dependable communication, these mechanisms are further constrained by the need to meet the latency requirements of the services.

In this section, we first describe basic concepts of service protection. Afterwards, we describe how to apply replication & elimination (R/E) to multiple domains, followed by a discussion of two options for replication in the 5G domain.

3.1 Basic Concept of Service Protection

3.1.1 Service Protection Mechanisms

Service protection methods can be classified based on the number of paths considered for forwarding as follows:

1. A single path is used. If a failure is detected on this path, a new path can be provisioned reactively. For example, single-path-forwarding is commonly employed in basic Layer-2 Ethernet networks like with the spanning tree protocol or the Media Redundancy Protocol (MRP) targeting low and bounded recovery time in ring topologies.
2. Multiple paths are used. Proper paths are selected based on node state information. For example, this is commonly employed in meshed Layer-3 IP networks.

Figure 11: Overview of path selection strategies

In the case of multiple paths, the path selection can either be controlled by the endpoints (if the endpoint is aware of the multiple paths and their characteristics) or by the network nodes. There are various path selection strategies (see Figure 11):

- a) **Best path selection:** Even if multiple paths are available, only the best path is used for forwarding. This procedure is usually accompanied by a fitness function that ranks the available paths (e.g., latency). If the selected path fails at runtime, the procedure is repeated to reactively provide a new path (if available).
- b) **Load balancing:** Multiple paths are used simultaneously. A path selector (a.k.a.) load balancer dynamically selects a forwarding path for each packet. As a result, frames can still be forwarded even if there is a single link failure (and it has been correctly detected). There exist various policies to determine a suitable set of forwarding paths (e.g., equal cost/delay, unequal cost/delay, or load based). Choosing a policy depends on the application requirements (e.g., on the time-criticality of the traffic) and on the desired bandwidth efficiency (e.g., when considering a throughput optimization objective).
- c) **Active/Standby redundancy (1:1(n)):** One of the paths is selected as the “active path” (a.k.a. primary path) and used for forwarding. Further paths are not set up and do not participate in forwarding (a.k.a. standby path(s)). They can be activated (e.g., via signaling) if the active path fails. Consequently, there still must be sufficient resources allocated on the standby paths to allow for a seamless transition upon failure detection of the primary path.
- d) **Active/Active redundancy (1+1(n)):** All paths are set up and used to forward traffic. One of them is selected as primary path, all the others are backup paths. The ingress node replicates all packets and sends them over all the paths (primary + backup(s)). At the egress node packets received over the primary path are forwarded, all other packets are dropped. If the primary

path fails, the ingress/egress nodes exchange signaling about which backup path should become active.

- e) **Replication/Elimination based redundancy (per packet 1+1(n))**: Special form of active/active forwarding, where redundancy is achieved on a per-packet basis. During replication additional sequencing information is added to the packets, so replicas can be easily recognized at the elimination node. Elimination works according to the first packet wins method, i.e., the first packet is forwarded, and all the later arriving replicas are dropped.

Note: each OSI layer may use any of the multiple path scenarios over the connectivity provided by the underlying layers, e.g., QUIC or Multipath-TCP (MPTCP) at L4, routing at L3, bridging at L2, etc.

3.1.2 Per packet Replication/Elimination

Dependable services usually do not allow even temporary interruptions caused by the convergence of the path selection protocols. Therefore, the usage of per packet Replication/Elimination (defined by IEEE and IETF) is preferred. We provide an overview of the functionality supported in TSN and DetNet.

IEEE 802.1 – Frame Replication and Elimination (FRER)

The Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) Task Group (TG) is a part of the IEEE 802.1 Working Group (WG). For general information, see the IEEE 802.1 home page. The charter of TSN TG is to provide deterministic connectivity through IEEE 802 networks, i.e., guaranteed packet transport with bounded latency, low packet delay variation, and low packet loss. TSN TG has evolved from the former IEEE 802.1 Audio Video Bridging (AVB) TG.

The IEEE 802.1CB-2017 standard specifies procedures, managed objects, and protocols for bridges and end systems that provide identification and replication of packets for redundant transmission, identification of duplicate packets, and elimination of duplicate packets. It is not concerned with the creation of the multiple paths over which the duplicates are transmitted.

IETF – Packet replication, ordering, and elimination functions (PREOF)

The IETF Deterministic Networking (DetNet) Working Group focuses on deterministic data paths that operate over Layer 2 bridged and Layer 3 routed segments, where such paths can provide bounds on reordering, latency, loss, and packet delay variation (jitter), and high reliability. DetNet solutions apply to both wireless and wired networks. The Working Group addresses Layer 3 aspects in support of applications requiring deterministic networking. The Working Group collaborates with IEEE 802.1 Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN), which is responsible for Layer 2 operations, to define a common architecture for both Layer 2 and Layer 3.

RFC 8655 describes a service protection method that sends copies of the same packets over multiple paths. The DetNet service sub-layer includes the PRF (Packet Replication Function), PEF (Packet Elimination Function), and POF (Packet Ordering Function) for use in DetNet edge packet processing, relay node packet processing, and end-system packet processing. These functions can be enabled in a DetNet edge node, relay node, or end system. The collective name for all three functions is Packet Replication, Elimination, and Ordering Functions (PREOF).

3.1.3 Operation of Per-Packet Replication and Elimination (R/E)

Per-packet replication and elimination does not react to and correct failures; it is entirely passive. Thus, intermittent failures, mistakenly created packet filters, or misrouted data are handled just the same as equipment failures that are handled by typical routing and bridging protocols.

The per-packet replication and elimination concept requires a minimum set of parameters during PEOF/FREER processing, namely:

- a) FlowID/StreamID: An integer identifying the Flow/Stream to which the packet belongs.
- b) SequenceNumber (SeqNum): An unsigned integer identifying the order in which the packet was transmitted relative to other packets in the same Compound Flow/Stream.

Note: The size of these parameters is implementation and encapsulation specific.

The entities listed in the following are used to implement the per-packet replication and elimination concept in a network. We note that some functions (e.g., encapsulation, sequence generation, individual recovery) are intentionally left out for simplicity.

- **Flow/Stream identification:** Packets received from the upper/lower layer are examined to determine to which flow/stream the packet belongs. This function helps to find out what redundancy related processing(s) (e.g., replication / elimination) is needed at a given hop.
- **Replication:** Member flows/streams are created via generating copies of packets and sending them on separate paths towards the destination. It provides the same SeqNum for the copies to allow elimination of any replicas.
- **Elimination:** Operation on a merged set of member flows/streams to eliminate duplicate packets (replicas). It forwards only the first received copy of a given packet and drops all other replicas of the packet. There can be various strategies/algorithms for elimination, e.g., IEEE 802.1CB-2017 defines two methods, namely the VectorRecoveryAlgorithm and the MatchRecoveryAlgorithm.
- **Traffic Steering/Engineering:** Provides different paths for the member streams across the network between the replication/elimination points.

Figure 12: Per packet replication (R) and elimination (E) operation in a packet transmission from source (S) to destination (D).

Figure 12 shows a network scenario where per packet replication/elimination is used between the source (S) and destination (D). The source is dual-homed to the network, whereas the destination is single homed. The Compound Flow is transported using five Member Flows (R1->R2, R1->E1, R2->E1, R2->E2, E1->E2,) over the nodes applying replication (R1, R2) and elimination (E1, E2) functionalities.

If member flows/streams that take different-length paths through the network are combined, a merge point may require extra buffering to equalize the delays over the different paths. This equalization

ensures that the resultant compound flow/stream will not exceed its contracted bandwidth even after one of the paths is restored after a failure. The extra buffering can be also used to provide in-order delivery.

3.1.4 Side effects of per packet R/E on latency

Per packet R/E results in “smoothing out” and reduction of the packet delay and packet delay variations. With redundant paths, the likelihood of multiple paths simultaneously undergoing higher packet delays becomes rare, and this results in overall lower delays and packet delay variations. This is because of the “first packet wins, later replicas are dropped” characteristics of the mechanism.

3.2 Usage of Domains: Multi-level R/E Concept

The entities implementing R/E functions must know two things for each received packet: (1) to which flow the packet belongs, and (2) which packets are essentially the same, i.e., are replicas of the same packet.

R/E entities have their own internal states and variables per flow. The design of R/E for a flow requires three steps. First, determine the number of maximally disjoint forwarding paths needed based on the network and flow characteristics. Second, design the location of R/E points in the network and the explicit fixed paths between them. Third, set flow and R/E instance related parameters. To provide the broadest possible service protection, the first replication and the last elimination points should be placed as close as possible to the source and the destination(s), respectively. However, R/E points can also be placed inside the network if the network topology allows and/or is beneficial to meet the service requirements.

Figure 13: Example placement of FRER/PREF entities in two domains (blue and yellow)

R/E functions are stateful and “propagate” their state information via the packet sequence number. As a result, for example, a reset of a sequence number generation function in one domain may cause packet drops in elimination nodes of other domains. This is because the same sequence number space is used end-to-end across all domains, thus making all these multiple domains a single failure domain. The overall robustness of a network can be improved by establishing failure domains and separating them from each other by using domain specific metadata (i.e., sequence number space), which we call multi-level R/E concept.

We propose introducing domain-specific sequence number spaces to enable the tailored provision of service protection in different domains, e.g., in different technology domains. A domain needs its domain-specific sequence number if the domain includes an elimination function for one or more streams/flows. This domain-specific metadata may be removed at the egress point of the redundancy

domain. TSN and DetNet specifications allow such a “push/pop” type operation of the sequence numbers. In the case of TSN, multiple R-Tags (forming a stack of R-Tags) can be carried in the Ethernet header. An example of multi-level R/E is shown in Figure 14, showing the corresponding VLAN tagging and the positions of the R-Tags. Analogously, in the case of DetNet, the aggregation functionality allows the use of multiple pseudowires and control words to store sequence information (d-CWs). However, the multi-level R/E concept in DetNet needs to be combined with its aggregation concepts, as the SeqNum is encapsulation-specific and cannot be pushed/popped on its own (see Section 3.1.3). Hence, due to its increased flexibility, the rest of this section is FRER specific.

Using the multi-level R/E concept provides FRER state independence (e.g., SeqGenReset) and allows adapting FRER settings to administrative domains. The concept uses a “Stack of R-Tags” and the most outer R-Tag is used within each domain by the FRER functions. R/E and push/pop actions are defined per domain and the domain borders are known only by domain edge nodes.

Figure 14: Multi-level R/E concept in a L2 network with 2 technology domains (blue and green)

Figure 14 shows the usage of the Multi-level R/E concept in an L2 network, where two technology domains (blue and green) are distinguished. Domain border nodes execute the addition (push) and removal (pop) operation of the domain specific R-Tags. Node-A (edge node of the blue domain) adds the level-1 R-Tag and Node-B (edge node of the green domain) pushes the level-2 R-Tag. The domain specific R-Tags are removed at the egress node(s) of the domain (i.e., Node-C and Node-D removes level-2 R-Tag of the green domain, and similarly Node-E removes the blue domain specific level-1 R-Tag).

3.3 Replication in the 5G Domain

The mobile network by default does not provide any explicit redundancy features for handling the failure of network entities, such as Base Stations (BS). Some redundancy may however be available due to the possible overlapping of the coverage areas of multiple base stations. However, it should be mentioned that the main motivation behind the deployment of more BSs is not to provide redundancy, but to increase the system capacity. The basic case is when a mobile device is equipped by a single UE. In the case of overlapping mobile cells some basic reliability is possible. If the serving BS fails, then the UE detects this via a Radio Link Failure (RLF). If neighboring mobile radio cells are available, then the UE will be able to reconnect to another base station and the connection between the mobile device and server can be restored. The fundamental problem with this option is the length of the failover time (detection of RLF + reconnecting to another BS), which practically is often much longer than the tolerable failover time of a mission-critical service.

Therefore, it is worthwhile to consider replication and elimination approaches also for 5G/6G networks as discussed next.

3.3.1 R/E as an Overlay Solution

Regarding the TSC defined in the current (Rel-19) 3GPP standards, no FRER/PREOF functionality is defined inside the 5GS. However, implementation of FRER/PREOF in the TSN Translator (TT) functions is not precluded. Therefore, for scenarios where high reliability is needed, the R/E can be added to the end-to-end path as an overlay solution. This means that replications happen before the traffic (TSN Stream / DetNet Flow) enters the 5GS and the member streams/flows are transported as disjoint as possible over the 5GS (using separate UE, separate PDU session, separate eNB, separate UPF).

Figure 15: Using disjoint resource over the 5GS components

Any mobile device can be equipped with multiple UEs, but the proper connectivity management of UEs in order to provide independent paths with high reliability over the mobile network is not addressed in the current mobile networks, neither in the case of attachment nor in the case of a handover (of one or multiple UEs) because there are no existing mechanisms in a mobile network, which guarantees that the two UEs are connected to independent network elements. The reliability is

not considered in the case of handover – the handover of one of the UEs belonging to the same device can result in a case where the two UEs will be connected to the same base station after the handover, which results in decreased overall reliability provided for certain devices by the mobile network. So, such a reliability handling mechanism is needed in the mobile network, which guarantees that the required reliability level will be provided for a certain device.

Figure 15 provides a basic solution to realize a highly reliable mobile system which can provide two independent paths between industry devices. This is achieved by defining reliability groups for the networking entities. By having networking entities in more than one reliability group, redundancy is achieved, which provides protection against failures.

Each industry device includes two or more UEs which belong to reliability group A, B, etc. The RAN offers redundant coverage, such that an area is typically covered by two or more base station (BS) entities, belonging to reliability group A, B, etc. The CN and transport network entities can also be redundant and belong to reliability group A, B, etc.

Normally, a UE belonging to reliability group A connects to a BS also in reliability group A, and then uses network entities also in group A to reach the UE in group A in the other industry device. Similarly, a UE belonging to reliability group B connects to a BS in group B, uses network entities in group B to reach the UE in group B in the other device. In this way, the two industry devices are connected by two communication paths that are independent, as shown in Figure 15.

Even though such a solution provides a basic approach to reliability by using duplicate paths between the communication endpoints, these solutions do not address the issues that may arise from device mobility and the resulting handovers. It may happen that the multiple UEs that are embedded in the device perform a handover at the very same time. This leads to a disruption in the communication where neither of the UEs in the device can communicate, which reduces the overall availability of the communication system. Even if the data packets can be delivered after the handover, this may be too late for critical communications.

The workaround for this mobility/handover problem is “handover coordination”. The RAN (or RANs) serving the UEs in the device get information about the timing of the handover process of the other UEs in the same devices. Based on the information, handover timing constraints are applied so that the gNB does not execute a handover when another UE of the device is undergoing a handover. In this way, the network coordinates the scheduling of the handovers so that the UEs in a given device will handover at non-overlapping times whenever possible.

The handover timing co-ordination may be based on pre-established schedules, or based on explicit signaling about a planned handover. When an gNB determines that a handover is needed, a handover lock is put into effect for the other UEs in the device. Such a locking mechanism can be based on a new logical network entity, or based on explicit signaling between the gNBs.

In the case of multiple UEs per device, for every UE the time allowed for handover (HO) execution could be defined as disjoint time periods of a certain time interval. An example for two UEs per device is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Allowed HO execution times for UE1 (green) and UE2 (blue) of the same URLLC device

Here, each UE has an HO execution time within each time interval ΔT , which is disjoint from that of the other, and also takes into account the maximum execution time (basically the maximum HO interruption time) for each of the UEs. This may be known by the network if the UEs signal specific value, e.g., at registration. Another alternative would be that the network uses a pre-configured value for the maximum HO interruption time. Yet another alternative is that the network continuously measures the UE HO interruption times and sets the allowed HO times accordingly.

3.3.2 R/E within the Mobile System

Although R/E functionality is not defined inside the 5GS, the implementation of FRER/PREOF in the TT functions are not precluded. When doing so, in general, the Multi-level R/E concept described in Section 3.2 can be used.

4 End-to-End Scheduling Algorithms for Multi-Domain Systems

In this section, we consider approaches for end-to-end scheduling in multi-domain systems including wired and wireless TSN bridges. We assume that intra-domain scheduling approaches are in place to forward messages with timing guarantees through a transit domain and within a domain from the talkers to border bridges and from border bridges to listeners. This facilitates a hierarchical approach for multi-domain systems distinguishing between the inter-domain level and intra-domain level, where at the inter-domain level, two questions need to be answered:

- How to split up the end-to-end latency budget between domains?
- How to support the aggregation and service protection concepts of Section 2.3/3.?

At the intra-domain level, local decisions for scheduling and routing are made to forward packets through the domain keeping the latency budget assigned from the inter-domain level.

In the following we start by discussing work that is related to inter-domain scheduling approaches. Based on this, we propose simple refinements to already existing scheduling techniques to answer the above questions.

4.1 Related Work

Our problem of real-time packet scheduling with multiple domains has similarities to multi-processor real-time task scheduling. In fact, one popular model for multi-processor task scheduling is the so-called *End-to-End Model* for cyclic tasks, that is described in [L00]. This model defines an end-to-end task, say T_i , as a sequence $(T_{i,1}, \dots, T_{i,n})$ of sub-tasks $T_{i,j}$, which have to be executed in the given order according to the so-called precedence constraint. That is, sub-task $T_{i,j+1}$ takes as input the output of task $T_{i,j}$. Consequently, the release time of $T_{i,j+1}$ (point in time when task becomes ready for execution) must be after the completion time of $T_{i,j}$. Moreover, the end-to-end task T_i has a given release time and deadline, whereas each sub-task $T_{i,j}$ has a given worst-case execution time $e_{i,j}$. Each sub-task is assigned to a processor, where a local scheduling algorithm, like Rate-Monotonic

Scheduling or Earliest Deadline First, schedules tasks on each processor independently. Even different scheduling algorithms can be used on different processors. For local scheduling, each sub-task must be assigned a release time and a deadline, which effectively splits the end-to-end latency budget (time between the release time and deadline of the end-to-end task) into local latency budgets for each sub-task (release time and deadline for each sub-task).

However, the sub-tasks of the End-to-End Model are not restricted to compute tasks. A sub-task can also be the transfer of data by a so-called network processor. Therefore, it is very interesting to consider how this model can be applied for multi-domain end-to-end, real-time communication in our case. To this end, we regard each domain as a processor of the end-to-end model, and sub-tasks as packets being forwarded through the domain within an assigned time budget (starting at a packet release time when the packet is received from the previous domain and until a local deadline to forward the packet to the next domain). To define packet release times and deadlines for each domain – i.e., for splitting the end-to-end latency budget – we consider existing algorithms for defining release times of sub-tasks and deadlines of sub-tasks of the end-to-end model in the next sub-sections in more detail.

4.2 Overview of Multi-Domain Scheduling and Synchronization

Next, we investigate how to apply the end-to-end model from real-time systems (see related work) to our problem of multi-domain end-to-end communication. We start with an overview of the assumptions before we discuss the details of each function.

Assumptions

We assume that all TSN domains are at least loosely synchronized, as described in Section 2.2. We solely consider time-triggered inter-domain streams (traversing multiple domains), where each stream F is specified by its inter-domain route, period, phase, and maximum frame size. Moreover, different listeners can have different QoS requirements, which capture end-to-end latency (time difference from the initial transmission at the talker to the arrival at the listener) and end-to-end reliability (relative number of frames arriving within the latency requirement).

Figure 17: Overview of end-to-end latency budget splitting

Approach

We build upon the scheduling approaches that we have previously presented in [DET24-D34]. Given an inter-domain stream aggregate $\{F_1, \dots, F_k\}$ or a service class (e.g., Gold, Silver, Bronze), we start by assigning a release time and deadline to each TSN domain. This information can then be used by the domains' CNCs for their local scheduling decisions, e.g., using the techniques described in [DET24-D34]. One of the main difficulties of this budget splitting approach is the need to synchronize neighboring domains. For instance, consider the two neighboring TSN border bridges of Domain 1 and Domain 2 in Figure 17. With each domain scheduling independently, the frame arrival order at the (egress) border bridge of Domain 1 likely differs from the expected transmission order at the (ingress) border bridge of Domain 2. We therefore require that each TSN border bridge has a dedicated hold-and-forward buffer for each stream aggregate and each service class that enables a potential reordering of stream aggregates between neighboring domains. Details on the end-to-end latency budget splitting and domain synchronization are provided in Section 4.3.

Moreover, while [DET24-D34] provides a good starting point for per-domain scheduling, it does not yet support the stream aggregation and replication techniques required by Section 2.3 and Section 3. We therefore recall the relevant details of the Disjunctive Graph Model and expand them to support stream aggregation, multipoint trees, and FRER. The details can be found in Section 4.4.

4.3 End-to-End Latency Budget Splitting and Synchronization

To enable each TSN domain to schedule independently from its neighboring domains, we split the end-to-end latency budget of each inter-domain stream aggregate (or service class) along its forwarding tree in Section 4.3.1. This provides each TSN domain with a release time and (relative) deadline for the stream aggregate. Still, there remains a less obvious problem even after the budget splitting: In Figure 17, consider two stream aggregates that traverse the domains $D_1 \rightarrow D_2 \rightarrow D_3$ with

- Stream Aggregate S_1 : Release time and deadline of $5ms$ and $10ms$ in domain D_2 , and
- Stream Aggregate S_2 : Release time and deadline of $1ms$ and $9ms$ in domain D_2 .

Due to local scheduling decisions in D_2 , it can still occur that S_1 arrives at the bridge B_2^2 (see Figure 18) before S_2 . The question then becomes: *When should S_1 and S_2 be forwarded to the domain D_3 , and in which order?* We discuss suitable synchronization protocols in Section 4.3.2.

4.3.1 Latency Budget Splitting

Figure 18: Inter-domain forwarding tree of the stream F1

We show how to determine suitable release times and deadlines for the stream aggregate (or service class) within the individual domains. To this end, the central challenge is to satisfy the end-to-end latency requirements while also accounting for the frame replication and elimination points in the forwarding tree (see Figure 18). We proceed in two steps: First, we introduce simple budget splitting techniques for unicast paths. Second, we provide a simple heuristic for incorporating the unicast splitting techniques into the general case of arbitrary forwarding trees.

Unicast Budget Splitting.

Consider a unicast path $T \rightarrow B_1^1 \rightarrow B_1^2 \rightarrow B_2^1 \rightarrow B_2^2 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_k^1 \rightarrow B_k^2 \rightarrow L$, where T is the talker, L is the listener, and B_i^1 (B_i^2) are the ingress (egress) border bridges of domain i . Moreover, let F be the stream under consideration with a total end-to-end latency budget $F.latency$. The required budget for transitioning domains $B_i^2 \rightarrow B_{i+1}^1$ is set to the bounded clock skew Δ , as discussed in Section 2.2. We denote the remaining budget by C in the following.

For assigning suitable budgets within the individual domains $B_i^1 \rightarrow B_i^2$, there are multiple options. The following provides a selection of simple heuristics for this assignment:

- i. *Uniform Budget Splitting:* With a total of k domains, assign a budget of C/k to each pair of ingress/egress border bridges $B_i^1 \rightarrow B_i^2$.
- ii. *Proportional Budget Splitting:* While uniform splitting is arguably the simplest technique, it does not account for potential load differences in the individual domains. As the inter-domain controller has the global view of all inter-domain streams, it can assign a weighted splitting that also accounts for the number of inter-domain streams (denoted by W_i) that traverse the individual domains $B_i^1 \rightarrow B_i^2$. The assigned budget is then

$$C \times \frac{(1 + W_i)}{\sum_j (1 + W_j)}$$

As a special case, the budget of the first stream is determined with the uniform budget splitting techniques, since $W_j = 0$ (for $j = 1, \dots, k$). Moreover, domains that contain wireless network elements should increase their corresponding weight to allocate more budget.

- iii. *Service Class Budget Splitting*: Each domain may also specify service classes (e.g., Gold, Silver, and Bronze as in Section 2.4.4) for the path $B_i^1 \rightarrow B_i^2$. We can thus also specify a heuristic that determines the stream-to-service-class assignment and derives the per-domain budgets accordingly. As this enables the utilization of bin-packing heuristics (e.g., next fit, first-fit, or best-fit), we only focus on how to derive the per-domain budgets: Let (P_i, Φ_i, L_i) denote the period, phase, and latency of the chosen service class in domain i . Instead of directly using L_i , the budget must also account for the phase shift in domain $i + 1$. Thus, when the frame is released at time $K_i \times P_i + \Phi_i$ at the ingress of domain i , the time of the earliest transmission slot in domain $i + 1$ is given by

$$K_{i+1} = \arg \min_k (K_i \times P_i + \Phi_i + L_i \leq k \times P_{i+1} + \Phi_{i+1}), \quad \text{with}$$

The budget then simply corresponds to the difference in the release times, i.e.,

$$K_{i+1} \times P_{i+1} + \Phi_{i+1} - (K_i \times P_i + \Phi_i).$$

Aggregation of Unicast Budget Splittings

```

FIXED  $\leftarrow \emptyset$ 
UNFIXED  $\leftarrow \{B_i^1 \rightarrow B_i^2 : \text{part of forwarding tree}\}$ 
while UNFIXED  $\neq \emptyset$  do
  Pick  $B_i^1 \rightarrow B_i^2$  from UNFIXED
  MINBUDGET $_i \leftarrow \infty$ 
  for each unicast path  $T \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_i^1 \rightarrow B_i^2 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow L$  do
    Compute unicast splitting (with budgets of FIXED)
    Let  $c_i$  be the resulting budget for  $B_i^1 \rightarrow B_i^2$ 
    MINBUDGET $_i \leftarrow \min(\text{MINBUDGET}_i, c_i)$ 
  end for
  FIXED  $\leftarrow \text{FIXED} \cup \{(B_i^1 \rightarrow B_i^2, \text{MINBUDGET}_i)\}$ 
  UNFIXED  $\leftarrow \text{UNFIXED} \setminus \{B_i^1 \rightarrow B_i^2\}$ 
end while
return FIXED

```

Algorithm 1: Aggregation of unicast budget splittings for general forwarding trees

Next, we derive generalized budget splittings for forwarding trees with multiple listeners and replication/elimination points. To this end, consider Algorithm 1: By iteratively fixing the budget for a pair of border bridges $B_i^1 \rightarrow B_i^2$ with the most stringent latency requirements (i.e., MinBudget), we utilize the unicast budget splitting techniques from above to derive the deadlines for each domain's egress border bridge B_i^2 .

To illustrate, the critical links of the forwarding tree in Figure 18 are $Talker \rightarrow B_1^1 \rightarrow B_2^1$, as it is the intersection of all three unicast paths:

- (i) $T \rightarrow B_1^1 \rightarrow B_2^1 \rightarrow L_2$,
- (ii) $T \rightarrow B_1^1 \rightarrow B_2^1 \rightarrow B_2^2 \rightarrow B_3^1 \rightarrow B_3^2 \rightarrow B_5^1 \rightarrow L_5$, and
- (iii) $T \rightarrow B_1^1 \rightarrow B_2^1 \rightarrow B_2^3 \rightarrow B_4^1 \rightarrow B_4^2 \rightarrow B_5^2 \rightarrow L_5$.

As described before, the budget of domain transitions $B_1^1 \rightarrow B_2^1$ is fixed to the clock skew bound Δ of the strong/loose time synchronization between domain D_1 and D_2 . Thus, the only undetermined

budget is that of $T \rightarrow B_1^1$: Assuming the unicast path (i) yields the smallest budget, say $5ms$, the paths (ii) and (iii) use the fixed budget in subsequent iterations to determine the budgets of the remaining links. Indeed, as there are no further critical links, all remaining budgets can be computed in one more iteration.

4.3.2 Inter-Domain Synchronization

As described before, the end-to-end latency budget splitting allows the individual TSN domains to schedule independently from their neighboring domains. This requires, however, that any two neighboring domains agree on the time when a stream aggregate should be forwarded between the two domains; otherwise, there could be uncontrolled frame reordering that potentially leads to unintended frame loss. In the following, we present well-known synchronization protocols from multi-processor task scheduling [L00] and discuss their applicability (along their advantages and disadvantages) to our multi-domain scheduling setting.

Figure 19: Overview of the Greedy Strategy and the Phase Modification Protocol

Greedy Strategy

The simplest strategy is a greedy strategy that forwards stream aggregates immediately, i.e., according to the strict priority transmission policy at the TSN border bridge. As depicted in Figure 19, Domain 2 may therefore receive a frame batch earlier than intended by the budget splitting of Section 4.3.1 (seen by the fact that the frame batches are forwarded over Link b before the deadline in Domain 1). In other words, the greedy strategy can be described as work-conserving, where the transmission link is never idle if there are frames enqueued at the egress border bridge of Domain 1.

The main advantage of the greedy strategy is that it does not require additional queueing capabilities for the egress border bridge of Domain 1. However, the problem of reordering frames is thereby simply deferred to Domain 2, where the respective ingress border bridge would require dedicated hold-and-forward buffers for each stream aggregate or service class. Without such buffers, the

injection of inter-domain streams would lead to uncontrolled frame reordering, with potential frame loss as a direct consequence.

Phase Modification Protocol

The *Phase Modification Protocol* [Bet94] is a non-greedy strategy for releasing sub-tasks in multi-processor scheduling, i.e., it can artificially delay the release of sub-task $T_{i,j}$ even if the predecessor task $T_{i,j-1}$ is already completed to shape the release time pattern of $T_{i,j}$. The earliest possible release time of a sub-task is calculated as the release time of the predecessor sub-tasks plus the worst-case execution time of $T_{i,j-1}$.

Translated to our multi-domain scenario, this means that the egress border bridge in Domain 1 has to enqueue each stream aggregate until the end of its dedicated budget (of Section 4.3.1). Compared to the greedy strategy that deferred the problem of frame ordering to the subsequent domain, the Phase Modification Protocol therefore requires the hold-and-forward buffers at the egress border bridge of Domain 1. In this regard, the Phase Modification Protocol also shares similarities with the Packet Delay Correction strategy that we discuss in another deliverable [DET24-D23] in more detail.

In general, the Phase Modification Protocol is a suitable choice if the following assumptions hold true:

- (1) The clocks of all domains are at least loosely synchronized.
- (2) The egress border bridges are equipped with dedicated hold-and-forward buffers for each stream aggregate and each service class.
- (3) The release times are fixed at all TSN domains and are known a priori, e.g., as specified by the end-to-end latency budget splitting.

Release Guard Protocol

So far, we have seen that the greedy strategy requires additional hold-and-forward buffers at the ingress sides of all domains, whereas the phase modification protocol requires hold-and-forward buffers at the egress sides. In contrast, the Release Guard Protocol [Sun97] can be seen as an intermediate strategy that aims for a more balanced queuing requirement on both the egress and ingress sides.

Figure 20: Overview of the Release Guard Protocol

The Release Guard Protocol operates as shown in Figure 20: Each egress border bridge maintains a state $r(S)$ that denotes the timestamp when the stream aggregate S was last forwarded to the

neighboring domain. The decision when the next frame batch of S should be forwarded is then made according to the following rules:

- (i) When $r(S)$ is not set, an initial policy decides when to forward the frame batch. For instance, it can be forwarded greedily, or it can wait until the deadline (similar to the Phase Modification Protocol). The state $r(S)$ is initialized accordingly. In Figure 20, the greedy policy is selected for the first transmission.
- (ii) When $r(S)$ is set, let t_A denote the arrival time of the frame batch at the egress border bridge. If t_A is later than $r(S) + period$, then the frame batch is immediately forwarded. Otherwise, the egress border bridge has to enqueue S in a dedicated hold-and-forward buffer until time $r(S) + period$. Similarly, the state $r(S)$ is updated to $\max(t_A, r(S) + period)$.
- (iii) As a special case of (ii), we also allow the frame batch to be forwarded earlier than $r(S) + period$, whenever the ingress border bridge sends a “Ready for Packet Delivery” notification (see Section 2.4). The state $r(S)$ is then updated to the time offset specified in the notification.

Similar to the Phase Modification Protocol, the Release Guard Protocol is not work-conserving as it does not forward the frame batches immediately to the neighboring domain. In contrast to the Phase Modification Protocol, however, the Release Guard Protocol may not wait until the exact release time that is dictated by the end-to-end latency budget splitting. Instead, the egress border bridges may also forward frame batches whenever they receive a “Ready for Packet Delivery” notification. By updating the state $r(S)$ as described in (iii), the subsequent release time $r(S) + period$ can also be earlier than what is dictated by the budget splitting.

4.4 Supporting Aggregation and Replication Concepts

After determining the level of stream aggregation and replication in Section 2/Section 3, and computing the effective release times and effective deadlines for each stream (resp. stream aggregate) in each domain, it remains to show how these concepts are supported for the domain’s scheduling algorithms. To this end, we extend the Disjunctive Graph Model (DGM) for multi-domain scheduling. Disjunctive graphs are widely considered in job-shop scheduling due to their explicit graphical representation of each job operation and the inter-job dependencies. The model was first adjusted for IEEE 802.1Qbv scheduling in [Egg24]. In the following, we start by recalling the necessary DGM background, as previously presented in [DET24-D34]. We then extend the DGM to support both multipoint and FRER and evaluate the positive effects this can have on both reliability and latency in the 5G-TSN setting.

4.4.1 The Disjunctive Graph Model for IEEE 802.1Qbv Scheduling

Figure 21a: Network topology

Figure 21b: Transmission Order

Figure 21: The disjunctive graph with a selected transmission ordering (b) for a simple topology (a).

Disjunctive Graph Selections:

For a given network topology — or, specific for multi-domain scheduling, the topology of the local domain — and a set of time-triggered streams \mathbf{F} , the disjunctive graph introduces a vertex O_f^i for each stream $F \in \mathbf{F}$, each frame $f \in F$, and each transmission hop i . For instance, the vertex $O_{f_2}^2$ in Figure 21 represents the transmission start of frame f_2 at its second transmission hop $[B_1, B_2]$. A disjunctive graph selection then determines the transmission ordering at each egress port by defining temporal dependencies between the transmission operations. In the case of Figure 21b, there are two categories that we illustrate through two representative examples:

- $O_{f_1}^1 \rightarrow O_{f_1}^2$ defines that the transmission of f_1 may only start at its second hop $[B_1, B_2]$ once the transmission over the first hop $[T_1, B_1]$ has finished.
- $O_{f_1}^2 \rightarrow O_{f_2}^2$ determines that the frame f_1 should start the transmission at $[B_1, B_2]$ before f_2 .

Shuffle Graphs:

Figure 22: Derived shuffle graph from the transmission ordering of Figure 21

With the transmission ordering of Figure 21 and the stream specifications \mathbf{F} , we derive shuffle graphs to provide a graphical representation of the IEEE 802.1Qbv configuration. While we provide an informal description of how to derive shuffle graphs, a more detailed description is given in [Egg24]. The procedure can be split into two steps:

1. *Add Fault Isolation Edges:* Whereas the transmission ordering in Figure 21 only specifies that f_1 should be transmitted via $[B_1, B_2]$ before f_2 and f_3 , it does not yet encode the FIFO queueing requirements. Moreover, we aim for fault isolation between different frames, i.e., each frame f_i should take its intended transmission slot independent of potential transmission faults experienced by any f_j ($i \neq j$). We therefore add FIFO edges of the form $O_{f_1}^2 \rightarrow O_{f_2}^1$ that ensures that f_2 is not enqueued “too early” at $[B_1, B_2]$. In detail, f_2 should only arrive at B_1 once transmission slot of f_1 ended. This guarantees that f_2 does not take f_1 ’s transmission slot, even if f_1 experienced a transmission fault (e.g., and was discarded by PSFP).
2. *Add Transmission Weights:* Next, each edge is given a weight to separate two temporal dependent transmission operations. We show this step for representative edges in Figure 22:
 - a. $0 \rightarrow O_{f_2}^1$ is weighted with $1ms$. This denotes that the frame f_2 is released at time $1ms$ (relative to the hypercycle) at its first hop.
 - b. $O_{f_1}^1 \rightarrow O_{f_1}^2$ is weighted with $10ms$. In the case of the first transmission hop $[T_1, B_1]$, this denotes the maximum packet delay from the transmission start at T_1 to the time of enqueueing the frame at B_1 . For 5G transmissions, the $10ms$ may be chosen according to given 5G packet delay histograms to reach a certain reliability guarantee [Egg24]. For an Ethernet link $[B_1, B_2]$, however, the packet delay simply corresponds to the sum of transmission delay $f_1.size / d_{rate}([B_1, B_2])$, propagation delay of $[B_1, B_2]$, and processing delay of B_2 .
 - c. $O_{f_1}^2 \rightarrow O_{f_2}^1$ is weighted with $-1ms$. This denotes that T_1 can start the transmission of f_1 already $1ms$ before the transmission of f_2 completed at $[B_1, B_2]$. In other words, a negative weight can be appropriate if the packet delay of f_2 via $[T_1, B_1]$ is known to take at least $1ms$, and that there is no chance of f_2 being enqueued earlier (e.g., as enforced by PSFP at B_1).

Deriving IEEE 802.1Qbv Configurations

Shuffle graphs provide an efficient way to derive a GCL and PSFP configuration in a single traversal. In particular, the longest path from 0 to the vertex O_f^i encodes the transmission start of the frame f at its i th transmission hop. As shuffle graphs are constructed to be acyclic [Egg24], the longest path can be computed in a single depth-first search traversal. With the transmission starts and known packet delay bounds, it is also straight-forward to compute the PSFP configuration for the next bridge.

For instance, for the operation $O_{f_2}^2$ the longest path in Figure 22 is given by

$$0 \rightarrow O_{f_1}^1 \rightarrow O_{f_1}^2 \rightarrow O_{f_2}^2$$

with an accumulated weight of $19ms$. This encodes that the bridge B_1 can start the transmission of f_1 via $[B_1, B_2]$ at time $19ms$. This information is then encoded in the GCL by opening the gate at time $19ms$ and closing the gate at time $19.1ms$ (with a maximum packet delay of $100us$ over $[B_1, B_2]$). Similarly, the expected arrival of f_2 at B_2 is $19.1ms \pm 1us$ (e.g., including a time synchronization error) that can be used to configure PSFP.

4.4.2 Extensions to the Disjunctive Graph Model

Supporting Stream Aggregation

The Disjunctive Graph Model naturally supports the described stream aggregation concepts of Section 2. That is, instead of modelling a vertex O_f^i for each transmission of *each frame* f , shuffle graphs can

be constructed with a vertex O_B^i for the i th transmission hop of a *frame batch* B . In particular, as stream aggregates of time-triggered streams continue to adhere to time-triggered traffic patterns (i.e., periodic traffic with a known route, phase and maximum batch size in bytes), the above construction procedure for shuffle graphs has all required parameters to determine the edge weights. The same holds true for the service classes (e.g., Gold, Silver, Bronze).

Supporting Multipoint Trees

Figure 23: Multipoint support in the Disjunctive Graph Model

Similarly, the model can be extended to cover multipoint trees by extending the available precedence constraints. That is, compared to unicast precedence chains of the form

$$0 \rightarrow O_{f_1}^1 \rightarrow O_{f_1}^2 \rightarrow O_{f_1}^3 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow O_{f_1}^{n-1} \rightarrow O_{f_1}^n \rightarrow *,$$

we allow multiple operation successors like $O_{f_1}^1 \rightarrow O_{f_1}^{2,1}$ and $O_{f_1}^1 \rightarrow O_{f_1}^{2,2}$ as in Figure 23. The frame f_1 is thereby duplicated at the bridge B_1 and the operations $O_{f_1}^{2,1}$ and $O_{f_1}^{2,2}$ denote the next transmission via the egress ports $[B_1, B_2]$ and $[B_1, B_3]$, respectively.

There is an apparent trade-off that comes with this extension. On the one hand, the frame duplication at B_1 improves bandwidth efficiency as f_1 does not have to be sent twice via the link $[T_1, B_1]$. On the other hand, having a single multipoint tree instead of multiple unicast paths complicates fault isolation; that is, as typical isolation constraints (e.g., the added fault isolation edges in Section 4.4.1) ensure that the frame f_1 does not arrive at B_1 too early so that it does not take an earlier transmission slot, the same now has to be ensured for all egress ports that are a part of the multipoint tree (i.e., $[B_1, B_2]$ and $[B_1, B_3]$). This results in a reduced solution space for finding suitable IEEE 802.1Qbv configurations.

Supporting Frame Replication and Elimination

Figure 24: Options for supporting Frame Replication and Elimination in the Disjunctive Graph Model

Compared to multipoint support in the Disjunctive Graph Model, the scheduling techniques required to support Frame Replication and Elimination (FRER) can be considered to be a generalization. In particular, the IEEE 802.1Qbv scheduler has to account for two additional details: First, the replication point adds an additional R-Tag and S-Tag to the frames (see Section 3), which has to be reflected in a changing frame size between the replication and elimination points. Second, the elimination points must require additional consideration, as shown in Figure 24. While the changing frame sizes are straight-forward to incorporate in scheduling, we discuss possible design choices for modelling the elimination points in the following:

1. **Unsynchronized Elimination Points:** This option includes explicit transmission slots for all frame replicas. For instance, there are two frame replicas in Figure 24a) that are transmitted via the egress port $[B_2, L_1]$. In case the first replica is lost, the transmission slot $O_{f_1}^{3,4}$ remains

empty and the second replica can be transmitted in the slot $O_{f_1}^{3,3}$ (when arriving at B_2). Otherwise, the first replica takes the transmission slot $O_{f_1}^{3,4}$ and the second replica is discarded by the elimination function at B_2 . More generally, this option incorporates a transmission slot for all N frame replicas, while only one of them will be used by f_1 at runtime.

2. **Synchronized Elimination Points:** Alternatively, IEEE 802.1Qbv scheduling has the capability to synchronize the frame replicas at the elimination point so that only one transmission slot has to be incorporated (e.g., $O_{f_1}^{3,1}$ in Figure 24b instead of $O_{f_1}^{3,3}$ and $O_{f_1}^{3,4}$ in Figure 24a). This can be achieved by adding additional precedence constraints in the Disjunctive Graph Model: $O_{f_1}^{2,1} \rightarrow O_{f_1}^{3,1}$ and $O_{f_1}^{2,2} \rightarrow O_{f_1}^{3,1}$, implying that the transmission operation $O_{f_1}^{3,1}$ can only be scheduled after both $O_{f_1}^{2,1}$ and $O_{f_1}^{2,2}$. While improving bandwidth efficiency, this option may also exhibit similar solution space impairments as with the multicast support.

In general, the better choice depends on the delay characteristics of the replication paths. Consider a frame f that is replicated across the paths R_1, \dots, R_N that are rejoined at the hop $[u, v]$ (i.e., bridge u is the elimination point). Using the synchronized elimination points option is preferable if the variation of the packet delays $d(R_i)$ is upper bounded by

$$d(R_i) - d(R_j) \leq (N - 1) \times \frac{f.size}{d_{rate}([u, v])}$$

where $f.size$ denotes the frame size of f and $d_{rate}([u, v])$ denotes the data rate of the link $[u, v]$. In contrast, the unsynchronized option would schedule N transmission slots for f at $[u, v]$.²

4.4.3 Evaluation

With the previously discussed options to support FRER in IEEE 802.1Qbv scheduling, we can take advantage of the “first packet wins” property of FRER in the 5G-TSN setting, as first observed by [VFF+23]. That is, when allocating 5G packet delay budgets $[d^{min}, d^{max}]$ for a single path as in [DET24-D34], the budget must be chosen large enough to exceed the reliability requirement $f.rel$, i.e.,

$$f.rel \leq \Pr(D \in [d^{min}, d^{max}]).$$

With multiple replication paths R_1, \dots, R_N , however, the requirement is relaxed to

$$f.rel \leq 1 - \prod_{i=1}^N \Pr(D_i \notin [d_i^{min}, d_i^{max}]).$$

² This heuristic can be extended in a straight-forward manner to a hybrid approach that only merges a subset of replication paths.

Figure 25: Impact of FRER on reliability (left) and latency (right) in a 5G-TSN setting. $N = 1, \dots, 4$ denotes the number of replication paths that traverse different logical 5G-TSN bridges.

Figure 25 shows the positive effects of this relaxation from an end-to-end perspective w.r.t. reliability and latency. That is, when the stream f is replicated across N different 5G links, the 5G packet delay budgets can be allocated to satisfy

$$\Pr(D_i \in [d_i^{\min}, d_i^{\max}]) \geq 1 - \sqrt[N]{1 - f.\text{rel.}}$$

Compared to a single path, the individual budgets $[d_i^{\min}, d_i^{\max}]$ are therefore considerably smaller.

On the one hand, this reduces the reliability requirement for each replication path (see Figure 25a), where a 90% per-replica reliability for $N = 4$ achieves an overall reliability guarantee of 99.999%. On the other hand, this also reduces $\max_i d_i^{\max}$ (see Figure 25b), where $N = 4$ can achieve a latency of below 8ms for all reliability requirements below 99.999%.

5 Conclusions & Future Work

In this report, we have presented system concepts and algorithms to support replication, aggregation, and scheduling techniques in multi-domain systems. Still, each domain continues to have full control over its local replication and scheduling decisions (e.g., as decided by the domain's CNC), which is especially important to certify that an industrial control system meets a certain safety integrity level. We summarize the key characteristics of our proposed multi-domain system architecture as

- **Inter-domain scheduling ability** that coordinates the scheduling decisions of the local domains. By splitting the end-to-end latency budget along the individual domains and synchronizing the forwarding time between two neighboring domains, we enable each domain to make individual scheduling decisions without requiring knowledge of global stream specifications.
- **Enabling fundamental stream aggregation concepts** that achieve a drastic reduction in the necessary state information that the bridges would otherwise have to maintain for each stream (in particular, to support fault tolerance mechanisms).
- **Inherent support for multi-level per-packet replication and elimination.** In extending previous scheduling capabilities to support replication and elimination, we enable the improved reliability and packet delay characteristics of FRER/PREOF in a multi-domain setting.

- **Relaxed time synchronization requirements** that ensure our presented concepts are also applicable in networks that do not support stringent time synchronization (e.g., a bounded clock skew of $1\mu s$ in IEEE 802.1AS) between every pair of network devices.

Altogether, these concepts yield the first steps to provide hard real-time guarantees in wide area network deployments that span across multiple technology and administration/configuration domains.

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List of abbreviations

CNC	Centralized Network Controller
CUC	Centralized User Controller
DetNet	Deterministic Networking
DetNet-PW	DetNet Pseudowire
DGM	Disjunctive Graph Model
COS	Class of Service
d-CW	DetNet Control Word
FIFO	First in, first out
FRER	Frame Replication and Elimination for Reliability
GCL	Gate Control List
GRE	Generic Routing Encapsulation

IP	Internet Protocol
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LSP	Label-Switched Path
MAC	Media Access Control
MPLS	Multiprotocol Label Switching
PD	Packet Delay
PB	Provider Bridging
PDC	Packet Delay Correction
PEF	Packet Elimination Function
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
POF	Packet Ordering Function
PREOF	Packet Replication, Elimination and Ordering Functions
PRF	Packet Replication Function
PSFP	Per-Stream Filtering and Policing
QoS	Quality of Service
R/E	Replication/Elimination
R-Tag	Replication Tag
S-Tag	Service Tag
SRv6	Segment Routing v6
TSC	Time-Sensitive Communication
TSN	Time Sensitive Networking
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
VLAN	Virtual LAN
VID	VLAN-ID
YANG	Yet Another Next Generation

Table 1: List of abbreviations